

Consumer Perceptions Of Price and Promotion On Airline Ticket Purchase Decisions at PT Pratama Mandiri Abadi

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to determine the company's ability to generate profits and to manage and allocate products through purchase decisions by analyzing consumer perceptions, price, and promotion at PT Pratama Mandiri, in order to identify which indicator has the most dominant influence on purchase decisions. The data collection techniques used in this research include observation, questionnaires, and interviews. The sampling technique applied was non-probability sampling using a purposive sampling method. The sample characteristics in this study were respondents who are currently purchasing or have previously purchased airline tickets at PT Pratama Mandiri. Data processing was carried out using quantitative analysis to calculate the number of respondents who answered the questionnaires. In the calculation, the researcher used percentage formulas and score interpretation. The price indicator had a score interpretation of 90%, the promotion indicator scored 86.8%, and the purchase decision indicator scored 88%. Among these three indicators, the purchase decision indicator received the highest score of 93.2%, indicating that it has the greatest influence compared to the other two indicators. The implementation of discounts during major holidays has proven effective in attracting consumer buying interest, thereby increasing the likelihood of consumers purchasing airline tickets at PT Pratama Mandiri.

Keywords: *Airline Tickets, Consumer Perception, Price, Promotion, Purchase Decision*

INTRODUCTION

Transportation facilities have a primary function of making it easier for individuals to visit a particular area. One type of transportation business is air travel services. Air travel offers advantages over land and sea transportation, especially in terms of the time it takes to reach a destination more quickly. The development of the transportation business has increased competition among service providers, which indirectly makes consumers more selective in their decision-making processes when choosing a product. A purchase decision is the action of deciding to buy a product, where consumers were previously presented with several alternative choices (Arfah, 2022). In the purchasing decision-making process, consumer perception plays a role. According to Yee in Wardhana (2022), consumer perception is formed through experiences about how they observe the services offered by a company and ultimately whether they are satisfied with the experience or not. According to Mustafa in

Edwin (2020), price plays an important role both macro- and microeconomically for consumers. For consumers, price can be a key consideration in making purchasing decisions, while for companies, price is the only element in the marketing mix that can generate revenue.

PT Pratama Mandiri is a company that collaborates as a travel agent with several airline companies such as Garuda Indonesia, Sriwijaya Air, Citilink, Lion Air, and Xpress Air. PT Pratama Mandiri is a subsidiary owned by the Employee Cooperative, which was established on October 20, 2003. The issue of airline ticket pricing, which is determined by the airlines, is constantly changing depending on the destination. In response to price fluctuation to build consumer trust, PT Pratama Mandiri Abadi offers a rescheduling and refund process that takes only 10 minutes from the time of customer complaint, and provides a 25% refund based on the ticket price offered. According to Tjiptono and Diana (2016:219), price is a component that directly affects company profit, and the price level influences the quantity sold.

In addition to price, promotion also influences purchasing decisions. According to Laksana in Noor (2021:70), promotion is a form of communication between seller and buyer, derived from accurate information, aimed at changing the attitude and behavior of the buyer—from initially unaware to becoming aware, making a purchase, and continuing to remember the product. PT Pratama Mandiri Abadi uses word-of-mouth (WOM) as its promotional medium. According to Kotler and Keller in Firmansyah (2020:296), word of mouth (WOM) is a process in which individuals or groups provide product or service recommendations personally, with the goal of sharing information on a personal level. Therefore, this research aims to determine the influence of price and promotion factors on airline ticket purchasing decisions at PT Pratama Mandiri.

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Consumer Perception

According to Julyanthry et al. (2022:37), is the stage in which an individual selects, organizes, and interprets sensations—sensations being the direct responses of the sensory receptors in the body (such as the eyes, ears, nose, mouth, or fingers) to basic stimuli originating from outside the individual, such as light, color, smell, texture, or sound. It can be understood that consumer perception influences how consumers choose and interpret information related to a product and how they assess a company. According to Priansa (2017:153), consumer perception can be shaped by several factors. These factors include:

1. Perceived Object

The object generates stimuli for the sensory organs that come from within or outside the individual who perceives, directly impacting the sensory nerves acting as receptors.

2. Sensory Organs

Nerves, and Nervous System these serve as tools to receive stimuli and generate responses through motor functions, which ultimately shape a person's perception.

3. Attention

Attention is the concentration or focus of an individual's total activity directed toward a group of objects.

According to Priansa (2017:153), consumer perception consists of several characteristics, namely:

1. Selective
2. Organized and Structured

3. Influenced by the Environment

b. Price

According to Swastha in Riyono & Budiharja (2016:101), price is the amount of money required to obtain a certain combination of goods and services. According to Siahaan (2019:34), price is the only element in the marketing mix that generates sales revenue; therefore, price affects the level of sales, profit margins, and market share that a company can achieve. It can be understood that price is a crucial component for a company to generate sales revenue, resulting in profit, and serves as a reference point for consumers when deciding to purchase a product. Failure to implement proper pricing strategies may lead to the company's failure. The objective of pricing goods or services should be directed toward achieving the company's overall goals. According to Tjiptono in Syahputra (2019:22), there are five main types of pricing objectives:

1. Profit-Oriented Objectives, every company aims to set prices that yield the highest possible profit.
2. Volume-Oriented Objectives, Companies set prices based on targeted sales volume, known as volume pricing objectives.
3. Image-Oriented Objectives, a company's image can be shaped through its pricing strategy.
4. Price Stability Objectives, In consumer markets, prices must be stable since consumers are highly sensitive to price changes.
5. Other Objectives, these include setting prices to prevent the entry of new competitors, retain customer loyalty, support repeat sales, or avoid government intervention.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012:52), there are four criteria that characterize price:

1. Price Affordability
2. Price Appropriateness in Relation to Product Quality
3. Price Appropriateness in Relation to Perceived Benefits
4. Price Suitability Based on Consumer Purchasing Power or Competitiveness

c. Promotion

According to Laksana in Noor (2021:70), promotion is communication between the seller and the buyer that originates from accurate information, aiming to change the buyer's attitude and behavior to recognize and remember the product. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2014:77), promotion is an activity that communicates the advantages of a product and persuades customers to purchase it. Promotion is one of the ways companies communicate with potential customers by delivering information and product knowledge intended to persuade them to make a purchase. In promotional activities, companies have specific goals they aim to achieve. According to Subagyo in Azmiani and Hidayat (2016), the objectives of promotion are:

1. To Inform, the primary objective is to inform consumers about all aspects and interests of the company that are related to them.
2. To Influence and persuade target customers, as a secondary objective, promotion aims to encourage customers to purchase the company's products.

3. To Remind, this involves reminding target customers of the company's existence, brand, and ongoing commitment to serving them, regardless of their location.

Kotler and Keller (2012:478) identify eight major tools in the marketing communications mix, namely:

1. Advertising
2. Sales Promotion
3. Events and Experiences
4. Public Relations and Publicity
5. Direct Marketing
6. Interactive Marketing
7. Word of Mouth
8. Personal Selling

d. Purchase Decision

According to Arfah (2022), purchase decision is one of the stages in the buying decision process where consumers are faced with several alternative choices and must decide whether to take action in purchasing a product based on the selected option. According to Kotler and Armstrong in Arfah (2022:4), purchase decision behavior refers to the final buying behavior of consumers, either individuals or households, who purchase goods and services for personal consumption. Kotler and Armstrong in Arfah (2022:6) identify several alternative indicators used to measure purchase decisions:

1. Problem or Need Recognition
2. Information Search
3. Evaluation of Alternatives
4. Purchase Decision
5. Post-Purchase Behavior

When buyers are satisfied with the product they have purchased, they will generally recommend the product or service to relatives and friends. Conversely, if they are disappointed, they will likely give feedback or criticism to the company that sold the product or service. The dimensions and indicators of purchase decision according to Kotler and Keller, as translated and adapted by Tjiptono in Arfah (2022:74–75), are:

1. Product Choice, consumers may decide to buy the product for a different purpose.
2. Brand Choice, buyers must decide which brand to purchase.
3. Dealer Choice, buyers must determine which seller or distributor to visit.
4. Purchase Timing, consumers may vary in their decision regarding the timing of the purchase.
5. Purchase Quantity, consumers may decide how many units of the product to buy at one time.
6. Payment Method, consumers decide which method of payment they will use.

METHODS

This study was conducted at PT Pratama Mandiri, located on Jalan Durian No.319 Komperta Plaju, Palembang City, South Sumatra. The data used in this study were obtained from consumer questionnaires who are currently or have previously made flight ticket purchases. In this study, primary data was used, consisting of interviews with the Director, the manager of the ticketing division, and consumer questionnaires.

The sampling technique applied was non-probability sampling using a purposive sampling method, population in this study consists of consumers who are in the process of or have made ticket purchases, and the sample was determined using the Roscoe theory, with a sample size of 50 respondents. Data analysis was conducted using a quantitative method with a Likert scale, where for each question, respondents would select one of five options representing their level of agreement with each indicator in the research variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As an initial step in understanding the phenomenon being studied, a descriptive analysis was conducted on 50 respondents classified based on the criteria of gender, age, occupation, and the airline tickets purchased by consumers. The data collected on gender criteria showed that 30 respondents, or 60%, were male, and 20 respondents, or 40%, were female. Based on gender criteria, the consumers of PT Pratama Mandiri are predominantly male.

Regarding the age criteria, the results showed that respondents aged 17-25 years accounted for 24%, those aged 26-30 years accounted for 26%, respondents aged 31-40 years made up 30%, those aged 41-50 years were 14%, and finally, respondents aged over 50 years were 6%. These results indicate that the most dominant consumer age group is 31-40 years. The descriptive analysis of the airline ticket purchases shows that Lion Air tickets had the highest number of purchases with 16 tickets out of the total, whereas Xpress Air tickets had the lowest number of purchases, with only 4 tickets sold.

After providing a general overview of the respondent characteristics, a data recap and quantitative analysis were conducted to evaluate the predetermined statistical parameters to identify significant patterns and relationships between variables. The analysis was performed on three variables used in this study: price, promotion, and purchase decision variables. The interpretation of respondent scores for each variable is presented in the table below:

Table 1: Variable Interpretation

Variable	Indicator	Score	Interpretation Score
Prices	Price Affordability	90%	Extremenly Strong
	Competitiveness	90%	Extremenly Strong
	Benefit		Extremenly Strong
	Appropriateness	91,2%	
	Quality Suitability	88,8%	Extremenly Strong
Promotion	Word Of Mouth	92.4%	Extremenly Strong
	Sales Promotion	88,8%	Extremenly Strong
	Advertising	79,2%	Strong

Variable	Indicator	Score	Interpretation Score
Purchase Decision	Problem Recognition	86,8%	Extremenly Strong
	Need	89,6%	Extremenly Strong
	Information Search	77,6%	Strong
	Evaluation of Alternatives	93,2%	Extremenly Strong
	Purchase Decision	89,6%	Extremenly Strong
	Post Purchase Behavior	90%	Extremenly Strong

As can be seen in the table above, starting with the Price variable, the price affordability indicator received an interpretation score of 90%, which falls into the very strong category. This indicates that the selling price of airline tickets offered is affordable relative to consumers' purchasing power and is able to provide ease of service to consumers.

For the Promotion variable, the word of mouth indicator obtained an interpretation score of 92.4%, showing that consumers receive positive information and experiences from others regarding the travel service, which successfully attracts potential consumers to proceed with the purchase decision of airline tickets. In the Purchase Decision variable, the highest interpretation score was on the purchase decision indicator at 93.2%, indicating that consumer evaluation in purchasing airline tickets is influenced by the discounts offered on the tickets.

Table 2: interpretation of the average for each variable

Variable	Average Score	Interpretation Score
Prices	90%	Extremenly Strong
Promotion	86,8%	Extremenly Strong
Purchase Decision	88%	Extremenly Strong

The average interpretation score of the three variables falls within the range of 81-100%, categorized as very strong. These results indicate that affordable prices affect consumer purchase decisions; in addition, the consumption variable also influences the purchase decision variable. Promotion provided by the company is a key element in the marketing mix that shapes consumer perception, positive attitudes, and interest in buying airline tickets.

For each variable, the lowest interpretation scores were found on specific indicators: for the Price variable, the quality suitability indicator; for the Promotion variable, the advertising indicator; and for the Purchase Decision variable, the alternative evaluation indicator. These results suggest that consumers' trust in product quality is not yet optimal, promotion efforts are lacking, and consumers tend to compare with other agents, which affects their decision-making process when purchasing.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research analysis conducted, it can be concluded that:

1. The price variable and the promotion variable have a significant influence on the purchasing decision variable for airline tickets.
2. The purchasing decision indicator related to the implementation of ticket discounts has a significant effect in attracting consumer buying interest.

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